

LB, 1% PB incidence at harvest results in approximately 0.3% yield loss.

The magnitude of losses caused by PB is close to losses reported for other cultivars in field plot experiments in

Thailand and India. The modified single hill technique allows a preliminary estimate of yield loss in situations where it may be difficult to experiment with many blast severities. □

2. Response surface showing the relationship between yield loss (%), leaf blast (scale of 0-7), and panicle blast (% incidence, PBI) on IR50.

A new sheath rot (ShR) disease of rice identified in Tamil Nadu

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At the end of dry season 1990 (Apr-May), an unidentified ShR disease was observed on rice cultivars IR20 and TKM9 growing on experimental plots in Killikulam. Nearly 7% of rice plants at the boot leaf stage showed disease symptoms, mostly on the sheath enclosing the young panicle. Irregular, dark brown lesions covered much of the sheath. Panicles emerging from diseased plants were mostly black.

The pathogen was identified as *Curvularia lunata* (Walker) Boedijn (IMI

NO. 343370). To test pathogenicity on IR20, a single-grain 15-d-old culture was inserted between the flag leaf sheath and unemerged panicle at the boot leaf stage. The fungus produced characteristic ShR symptoms within 15 d. Symptoms on inoculated plants were similar to those on naturally infected plants.

Infectivity of the fungus was tested on other rice cultivars. A single-grain culture was inserted at the boot leaf stage. Test cultivars were transplanted at 2 seedlings/earthenware pot in insect-proof cages. Five replications of 10 seedlings each were used. Disease severity was scored 15 d after inoculation using a 0-9 scale: 0 = no disease, 1 = less than 1% sheath area affected, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, and 9 = 51-100% sheath area affected. ADT36, ADT38, IR50, ASD7, ASD8, and ASD17 were completely free of disease (see table).

Infectivity of *Curvularia lunata* on Tamil Nadu rice cultivars.

Cultivar	Damage score (0-9)
ADT36	0.0
ADT38	0.0
IR50	0.0
Co 37	5.6
MDU2	3.8
MDU3	5.7
ASD1	7.8
ASD2	9.0
ASD3	1.9
ASD4	2.8
ASD5	2.5
ASD6	4.8
ASD7	0.0
ASD8	0.0
ASD9	3.5
ASD10	5.4
ASD11	3.8
ASD12	7.5
ASD13	8.6
ASD14	3.0
ASD15	7.0
ASD16	5.5
ASD17	0.0
IR20 (check)	9.0
TKM6 (check)	9.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.7

The result was confirmed by a repeated experiment.

Several species of *Curvularia* are known to infect the rice grain, and may even cause leaf spots and seedling blight under certain conditions. But ShR due to *Curvularia lunata* had not been reported previously. □

Effect of asynchronized rice planting on vector abundance and tungro (RTD) infection

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Variation across fields in time of planting the rice crop lengthens the period for an increase in insect pests and diseases and shortens the fallow period during which the numbers of many pest species decline. Insect-transmitted diseases such as RTD are expected to be more prevalent in asynchronously planted areas, because their vectors are